

Artificial Intelligence and Gender Equality: The Usage of Technology and the Problems in Education

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Abstract

The paper explores the impact of technology, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI), on education and gender equality. It discusses six main aspects that need careful consideration. These include access to education, addressing gender biases in educational content, providing teacher training and support, promoting digital literacy, and closing the gender digital divide, ethical considerations, and the risk of technology reinforcing inequalities. The conclusion emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach, combining technology with inclusive policies, teacher training, digital literacy initiatives, and ongoing evaluation to maximize benefits and address challenges in achieving gender equality in education.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI); Education; Gender Equality; Practice of Gender Equality Education; Technology